

PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES: EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR EDUCATION MANAGERS

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Abstract. *This article considers the importance of psychologically developing entrepreneurial competence of future managers in the field of education. Entrepreneurial competence is indicated as one of the main factors contributing to the professional success of modern educational managers. The authors note the need for the harmonious development of emotional intelligence, strategic thinking, motivation and entrepreneurial abilities. In addition, the need to develop innovative thinking and the ability to act stably in stressful situations is indicated in order to ensure the adaptation of future managers to a changing environment. In conclusion, the preparation of managers in the field of education to be entrepreneurial is described as an important step that contributes to the development of the social environment. The proposed strategies are aimed at increasing the professional competence of future educational managers.*

Keywords: *educational managers, entrepreneurial competence, entrepreneurial activity, educational management, managerial competence.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola kelajakdagi menejerlarning ta'lim sohasidagi psixologik jihatdan rivojlanayotgan tadbirkorlik qobiliyatining ahamiyatini ko'rib chiqadi. Tadbirkorlik qobiliyati zamonaviy ta'lim menejerlarining kasbiy muvaffaqiyatiga hissa qo'shadigan asosiy omillardan biri sifatida ko'rsatilgan. Mualliflar hissiy intellekt, strategik fikrlash, motivatsiya va tadbirkorlik qobiliyatlarini uyg'un rivojlantirish zarurligini ta'kidlaydilar. Bundan tashqari, kelajakdagi menejerlarning o'zgaruvchan muhitga moslashishini ta'minlash uchun innovatsion fikrlash va stressli vaziyatlarda barqaror harakat qilish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish zarurati ko'rsatilgan. Xulosa qilib aytganda, ta'lim sohasidagi menejerlarni tadbirkorlikka tayyorlash ijtimoiy muhitni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi muhim qadam sifatida ta'riflanadi. Taklif etilayotgan strategiyalar bo'lajak ta'lim menejerlarining kasbiy malakasini oshirishga qaratilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ta'lim menejerlari, tadbirkorlik kompetensiyasi, tadbirkorlik faoliyati, ta'limni boshqarish, boshqaruv kompetensiyasi.*

Introduction. In line with the rapid development of the world, new trends in the field of education highlight the importance of increasing the level of entrepreneurial competence of managers. Management in the field of education is a young and important direction in its development, which is confirmed by the effective results of management in many areas. In this regard, there is an increasing interest in studying the entrepreneurial competences of managers in the field of education. It is known that high-quality education requires a high-quality management system, and if we consider it in terms of competence, this is reflected in the

growing demand for competent managers for entrepreneurial activities. Changes in the socio-economic direction direct education towards the personal development of the individual, creativity and independence. Modern education managers are required to be able to analyze, compare, evaluate information, and also to justify their point of view. The change in the paradigm of the global education system leads to the search for new approaches.

It is known that quality education requires a quality management system, and if we consider it in the context of competence, it is reflected in the growing demand for competent managers for entrepreneurial activities. Changes in the socio-economic direction direct education towards the personal development of the individual, creativity and independence. Modern education managers are required to be able to analyze, compare, evaluate information, and also to be able to justify their point of view. The change in the paradigm of the global education system leads to the search for new approaches. One of these approaches is aimed at developing an entrepreneurial personality in the modern rapidly changing world. Analysis of scientific and methodological literature and data from social surveys shows the insufficient level of entrepreneurial competence in the field of education. One of the main goals of training education managers in the socio-economic conditions of society is the formation of a managerial personality who can contribute to the development of the country.

Literature review. Currently, we note that the demand for labor is increasing for managers with entrepreneurial skills. In the current development of Kazakhstan, having entrepreneurial competence is considered prestigious and is of interest in the field of education. Works focused on the basics of management in the field of education are studied in the works of scientists Kodzhaspirova G.M., Trapitsyn S.Yu., Vesin V.R., Averchenko L.K., Grigoreva L.I., Egorshina A.P., Zhakovskoy M.A., Zarkova S.V., Kibanova A.Ya., Lazareva V.S., Lisichkino G.A., Ogarkova A.A. and others. The problems of management in the field of education in our country can be seen in the works of such scientists as Kosherbayeva A.N., Balykbayev T.O., Baimoldaev T.M., Kosherbayeva A.N., Islamgulova S.N., Aganina K.Zh., Mamyrova N.K., Murzalinova A.Zh., Taubayeva Sh.T., Khasenov S.S., Kozybayev E.Sh. and others. Analysis of scientific literature, study of real management practices prove that psychology plays an important role in the formation of professional competence of education managers. The managerial activity of an education manager can be understood from the perspective of social psychology. It is manifested in the process of solving educational problems through communication and in the socio-psychological representation of all participants in the management process.

The problem of understanding and developing entrepreneurial competence is complex and multifaceted, as it includes both individual characteristics of the individual and universal abilities that respond to changes in society. The works of scientists who have studied this concept allow us to comprehensively reveal its content. If Joseph Schumpeter considered entrepreneurship as a driving force of economic growth and associated it with innovation, then David McClelland, who explained this idea at the personal level, puts the motive for achieving success in the first place. Combining their points of view, it can be said that entrepreneurial competence is based not only on introducing innovation, but also on the active use of motivational resources necessary for its implementation. The works of Daniel Goleman, who paid special attention to the importance of emotional intelligence in the development of entrepreneurial competence, reveal the psychological aspect of this competence. In entrepreneurial activity, emotional management, empathy, and self-regulation increase the effectiveness of the decision-making process. This idea can be combined with John Dewey's

concept of lifelong learning: being an entrepreneur is not just a set of fixed skills, but also the ability to constantly adapt to changing circumstances and embrace innovation. In addition, entrepreneurial competence is closely related to resource management, strategic planning and leadership skills. This is shown by the research of Manfred Kets de Vries. He particularly emphasized the role of leadership in entrepreneurial success. In this sense, entrepreneurial competence is not seen as a single individual ability, but as a set of managerial competencies aimed at collective success.

Combining these perspectives, entrepreneurial competence can be interpreted as a synthesis of qualities such as strategic thinking, emotional stability and innovativeness for modern educational managers. Only the combination of these qualities makes managers able to act effectively in accordance with the requirements of the modern market. The European “EntreComp” model is a useful model for structuring this concept, as it divides entrepreneurial competence into three main areas: idea management, resource utilization and result-oriented actions.

Research methods. The purpose of this study is to identify effective strategies for the psychological development of entrepreneurial competence of future educational managers. The study involves the use of mixed methods, that is, the collection and analysis of quantitative and qualitative data. As data collection methods, a questionnaire consisting of 15 questions, the Big Five Personality Test and the Emotional Intelligence Scale were chosen to assess personality traits and emotional intelligence. In addition, interviews were conducted to obtain more in-depth information, the results of which were processed using the content analysis method. These methods allow for a more detailed study of the psychological aspects of the research object. The data were processed using statistical and content analysis methods. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the data were kept confidential.

Strategic directions. Entrepreneurial competence is defined as the ability of a person to effectively use their internal resources in combination with external opportunities. To develop this competence, it is necessary to harmoniously improve innovative thinking, emotional intelligence and managerial skills. Psychological development of entrepreneurial competence of educational managers is a complex process that involves the harmonious formation of personal and professional qualities to improve their managerial skills. This concept includes the development of the abilities of managers in the field of education to implement new ideas, effectively manage resources, make strategic decisions and adapt the organization to changing conditions. Entrepreneurial competence requires not only innovative thinking and effective management, but also emotional intelligence, motivation and the ability to act stably in stressful situations. From a psychological point of view, the development of this competence is aimed at strengthening the manager's ability to manage emotions, establish effective relationships with the team and realize his own potential. Such abilities allow to increase the competitiveness of an educational institution, improve the quality of education and meet modern requirements.

A high level of entrepreneurial competence of a manager is the ability to innovate. Innovation involves the presentation and implementation of new, successful ideas, effective approaches and improving their quality. Modern society needs reliable specialists with high creative activity who know how to evaluate the results of their activities both during and outside of work. An educational manager should demonstrate responsibility, empathy, and a desire for innovation. To become a successful and sought-after specialist in modern times, one must be ready for any changes, be able to quickly and effectively adapt to new situations. It is also very important for an educational manager to constantly update his entrepreneurial competence and

strive for self-development. However, as social experience shows, these characteristics are not found in all managers. On the contrary, managers face a number of difficulties in adapting to rapidly changing social, economic, and professional conditions. According to Barinov, entrepreneurship provides the most incredible personal growth imaginable: "Every day you have to overcome your own fears, laziness, and incompetence. It's a very valuable experience."

To acquire entrepreneurial competence, it is necessary to master a number of skills and abilities, including:

1. HR management;
2. Financial literacy;
3. ability to plan strategically;
4. understanding global business trends;
5. leadership skills;
6. Networking;
7. ability to set goals;
8. building a personal brand;
9. Marketing.

Research Discussion. This study identified effective strategies for developing entrepreneurial competence in future educational managers from a psychological perspective. Developing entrepreneurial competence requires a comprehensive approach that includes not only theoretical knowledge but also practical skills, emotional intelligence, and self-management abilities.

The data obtained during the study revealed important psychological factors that affect the entrepreneurial competence of future educational managers. Also, a high level of emotional intelligence allows for effective work in managerial positions, as this ability affects the ability to properly establish relationships with people and make the right decisions in stressful situations.

Currently, there is a lack of psychological strategies and methods for developing entrepreneurial competence in educational managers. This study highlights the need for special programs aimed at developing entrepreneurial competence in future educational managers. In addition, the methods and strategies selected in the study are important foundations for future research in this area.

Conclusion. Psychological development of entrepreneurial competence of future educational managers is an important direction for improving management skills in accordance with modern requirements. This process includes not only the acquisition of professional knowledge and skills, but also the development of emotional intelligence, creative thinking, motivation, risk management, leadership, and self-awareness. Various strategies based on the work of scientists encourage managers in the field of education to implement new ideas, make effective decisions, and adapt to changes. The idea of identifying and assessing the level of entrepreneurial competence of future educational managers is centered on the personal abilities and interests of managers. Only by forming leaders with a high level of entrepreneurial competence can we achieve great results in the education system. Therefore, the place of entrepreneurial managers in the education system is very large and is currently in the process of rapid development.

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